

The Impact of financial development on the economic growth and economic volatility.

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Abstract: This paper examines the impact of financial development on economic growth and economic volatility. Financial development, encompassing the provision of a broad range of financial services, plays a critical role in economic frameworks by creating savings and ensuring efficient investment through intermediation. Utilizing econometric modeling and empirical data analysis, this study investigates whether financial development promotes economic expansion and stabilizes or exacerbates economic fluctuations. The research question centers on identifying the statistical relationships between financial development, economic growth, and economic volatility. Hypotheses are tested using data from multiple countries over several decades. The findings aim to provide insights for policy-makers on leveraging financial development to achieve sustainable economic growth and stability, while also addressing the conflicting results found in existing literature on this topic.

Keywords: Financial Development, Economic Growth, Economic Volatility, Financial Intermediation, Savings Mobilization, Investment Efficiency, Business Cycle Fluctuations, Econometric Modeling, Empirical Data Analysis, Policy Implications

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Introduction

Financial development, and financial intermediation all refer to the provision of a broad range of financial services to meet various financial needs. These two words are used interchangeably in literature. There are two main economic avenues through which financial development is thought to influence economic growth. First, it creates savings (McKinnon, Citation1974). Second, it guarantees that the best prospects for return on investment are provided via effective intermediation. Hence, the importance of financial development for the healthy and viable framework of an economy cannot be ignored. Early in the 2000s, there was widespread agreement that finance played a significant role in promoting economic expansion. In essence, financial organizations distribute private and public savings across businesses and people. More effective expenditures would result from good financial development, which would boost the economy. Yet, after the onset of the global financial crisis, the notion that this connection is not entirely obvious began to gain ground. What effect does financial development have on economic expansion? Does finance enhance variety in economic growth around its pattern, or does it regulate the economic system's drive, helping to lessen business cycle fluctuations?

Research question

Is there a significant statistical relationship between the financial development, the economic growth and economic volatility?

Research hypothesis

H1a: there is no significant statistical relationship between the financial development and the economic growth.

H1b: there is significant statistical relationship between the financial development and the economic growth.

H2a: there is no significant statistical relationship between the financial development and the economic volatility.

H2b: there is significant statistical relationship between the financial development and the economic volatility.

Motivation

The area of economics is constantly changing and is influenced by a wide range of factors. Financial development, which has been found to have a substantial impact on both economic growth and economic instability, is one of these elements that is most crucial. As a result, research into how financial development affects these aspects is extremely essential and has the potential to have significant effects on both investors and politicians. Understanding how financial systems and institutions contribute to economic growth and stability is at the heart of the study of financial development. This can cover a wide range of topics, from how banks and other financial intermediaries help businesses get money to how financial regulations and financial policies affect the economy as a whole. Finding the finest methods and policies that can support long-term economic growth and stability is the ultimate goal of research on financial development. The effect of financial systems on economic growth is one of the main areas of study in the field of financial development. An increasing amount of research indicates that, in both developed and developing nations, financial development can have a considerable impact on fostering economic growth. For instance, a sound financial system can assist in mobilizing savings and directing them toward profitable investments, which can spur productivity and innovation growth. A strong financial system can also encourage resource allocation that is efficient, which lowers transaction costs and improves the performance of the economy as a whole. The effect of financial systems on economic volatility is a key field of inquiry within the study of financial development. Because it can cause uncertainty and instability in the financial markets, volatility can be a significant concern for both investors and governments. Therefore, it is crucial to do study into how financial systems might increase or decrease economic volatility. For instance, a sound financial system can contribute to lowering the risk of financial crises, which can therefore lower volatility and advance long-term stability. Overall, research into how financial development affects economic growth and volatility is very essential and has the potential to have significant effects on the world economy. We can determine the best practices and policies that can contribute to the creation of a more sustainable and prosperous future by better understanding the role that financial development play in fostering growth and stability.

Related literature

King and Levine (1993) conducted the first empirical investigation to assess the causal relationship between financial development and economic growth. In addition to GDP per capita growth, they utilized capital per capita growth and productivity growth as dependent variables to evaluate the pathways via which finance drives economic growth. In total, they used three key indicators of the development of financial intermediates. Their findings showed a favorable relationship between the economic growth indicators and the financial development metrics, and that the early financial development was a reliable indicator of subsequent long-term growth. Similar outcomes were discovered in related publications, such as Levine and Zervos (1998), which broadened the scope of financial development indicators to include stock market development variables. Levine et al. (2000) and Beck et al. (2000) reevaluated King and Levine's findings using instrumental indicators cross-section regressions and dynamic panel GMM approaches. According to LaPorta et al., the country's legal origin was the instrumental factor for financial development this was in accordance to LaPorta et al. (1998). In contrast to capital accumulation and the savings rate, the authors discovered that the financial

development has a positive effect on GDP and economic growth. Aghion et al. (2005) used a different method to examine the relationship between finance and growth. Although Aghion et al. (2005) proposed that financial development can hasten convergence to steady-state without changing steady-state growth itself, most analyses (at least implicitly) presume that financial development may change the rate of steady-state growth. In order to verify this, the research applied a cross-nations regression method and included an interaction term between the starting level of relative per capita GDP and the financial development indices. The findings confirm their hypothesis. According to certain research, the effect of finance on growth may change depending on the sophistication of the financial system. Levine et al. (2000)'s research was replicated by Rioja and Valev (2004), who divided the sample into three areas with varying levels of financial development. They discovered that the influence of growing financial development was weak in the area with weak financial development but significant in the area with medium financial development. Seven and Yetkiner (2016) looked at the individual effects of bank and stock market expansion and discovered that banking growth is advantageous to economic growth in middle-income and low-income economies, but detrimental in high-income economies. In contrast, stock markets encourage growth in high- and middle-income nations. Loayza and Ranciere (2006) made an effort to connect the financial meltdown literature with the literature on financial development, which supports the idea that indicators of credit may be employed to forecast crises and, as a result, have a detrimental effect on economic growth. They separated the long-run and short-run reactions of economic growth to private credit using a Pooled Mean Group technique and panel data, and they found that this association is positive over the long run. In the near term, however, the opposite happens, so financial development may be linked to financial volatility and crises. There are series of studies that looked at how financial development affected the volatility of GDP per capita growth, which is an indicator of economic growth. Little indications of an Inverted relationship between private lending and growth volatility was discovered by Easterly et al., (2001). The succeeding study, however, mostly advocated a linear relationship between financial development and volatility and discovered that this relationship was inverse or negative. Beck et al., (2006) made an effort to assess how financial development affects how monetary and real volatility affects growth volatility. They discovered that, especially if stock markets are immature, increased private lending may, respectively, lessen and raise the impacts of both monetary and real volatility. Additionally, Beck et al. (2014) separated the impacts of the financial systems' integration and non-integration activities on economic growth and growth volatility using a distinct indicator of financial development. Their major finding is that, over the long run, financial intermediation boosts growth while lowering volatility, but these impacts decrease when looking at more recent data. Yet, non-intermediation activities may cause volatility to rise in the medium term while having no long-term impact on growth or volatility. Mallick (2014) breaks down growth volatility into short-term and long-term components and shows that the growth of financial sector lowers short-term volatility but has no long-term impact. Previous studies provide empirical support for the theoretical relationship between financial development and macroeconomic indicators (Adu et al., Citation2013; Samargandi et al., Citation2015). However, these researches have looked at the effects of financial development on jobs, inflation, and economic expansion independently for diverse sets of countries over a range of time frames. Certain studies (Danilevica, et al., 2020; Wadud, 2009) have focused more on the causality path, whereas other studies have focused on the quantity and quality consequences of financial development (Christopoulos & Tsionas, 2004; Rachdi & Mbarek, 2011). These researches appears to support the close connection between financial development, economic expansion, as well as other related macroeconomic factors (Cheng et al., 2021; Nawaz et al., 2019). Recent research has found conflicting results about the influence of financial development and economic growth. Some studies have found a positive or direct relationship (Afonso & Blanco-Arana, 2018; Ahmad et al., 2018), while other researches have shown negative or inverse relationship (Ahmed, 2016; Ayadi et al., 2015). According to Rousseau and Wachtel's (Citation2011) study, the only way for financial development to have a beneficial effect on economic growth is if inflation is kept within or below the benchmark. Yet, once inflation has reached the predetermined level, the changes in the financial sector have little impact on the rate of economic expansion.

Data

Table 1: Summary descriptive statistic

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
GDPgrowth	900	3.605	3.793	-14.814	18.467
Outputvolatility	887	.283	.17	.009	.822
CPI	900	5.986	35.179	-4.466	1037.873
logGDPatmarketpric~a	900	26.213	2.05	15.979	30.731
Generalgovernmentf~p	900	17.385	4.847	5.094	28.61
TradeofGDP	900	91.657	61.291	19.286	439.997
Recessionperiod	900	.119	.324	0	1
Privatecreditbydep~y	889	65.356	42.329	5.389	262.678

GDPgrowth: This variable measures the annual percentage change in real GDP which indicates the Economic growth. The mean value is 3.605%, indicating that, on average, the economy around the globe has been growing at a moderate pace. However, the standard deviation of 3.793% suggests that the growth rate has been highly volatile and there are some countries registering extremely high or low economic growth as compared to the mean. The economic growth ranges from -14.814% to 18.467%.

Outputvolatility: This variable measures the standard deviation of the yearly percentage change in real GDP which indicates output volatility. The mean value is 0.283%, indicating that, on average, different economies’ output has been relatively stable over the years. The standard deviation of 0.17% suggests that the output has been fluctuating with a moderate level of volatility, ranging from a minimum of 0.009% to a maximum of 0.822%.

CPI: This variable measures the yearly inflation rate as measured by the Consumer Price Index. The mean value is 5.986%, indicating that, on average, prices have been rising at a moderate pace. However, the standard deviation of 35.179% suggests that the inflation rate has been highly volatile indicating some nations experience extremely high or low annual inflation rate as compare to the mean value, ranging from a decline of 4.466% to an increase of 1037.873%.

logGDPatmarketprice: This variable measures the natural logarithm of real GDP at market prices which indicates the economic size. The mean value is 26.213, indicating that, on average, the economies’ GDP has been at a high level. The standard deviation of 2.05 suggests that the GDP has been moderately dispersed around the mean, ranging from a minimum of 15.979 to a maximum of 30.731.

Generalgovernmentf~p: This variable measures the general government final consumption expenditure as a percentage of GDP. The mean value is 17.385%, indicating that, on average, different governments around the globe have moderate consumption expenditure relative to the GDP. The standard deviation of 4.847 suggests that the expenditure has been moderately dispersed around the mean, ranging from a minimum of 5.094 to a maximum of 28.61.

TradeofGDP: This variable measure trade openness. The mean value is 91.657%, indicating that, on average, the trade volume has been high relative to the GDP hence high level of trade openness. The standard deviation of 61.291% suggests that the trade volume has been highly volatile, ranging from a minimum of 19.286% to a maximum of 439.997%.

Recessionperiod: This variable is a binary variable that takes the value of 1 if the observation is within a recession period and 0 otherwise. The mean value is 0.119, indicating that, on average, about 12% of the observations are within a recession period. The standard deviation of 0.324 suggests that the recession period has been highly volatile,

Privatecreditbydep~y: This variable measures the private credit by deposit money banks as a percentage of GDP. The mean value is 65.356%, indicating that, on average, the private credit has been moderate relative to the GDP. The standard deviation of 42.329 suggests that the private credit has been highly dispersed around the mean, ranging from a minimum of 5.389% to a maximum of 262.678%.

Normality Test

Table 2: Shapiro-Wilk W test for normal of Economic Growth

Variable	Obs	W	V	z	Prob>z
GDPgrowth	900	0.951	27.924	8.210	0.000

H1: the variable economic growth is normally distributed

H2: the variable economic growth is not normally distributed

From table 2, the p value is less than 0.05 indicating that the data set for economic growth is not normally distributed.

Table 3: Shapiro-Wilk W test for normality of Output volatility

Variable	Obs	W	V	z	Prob>z
Outputvola~y	887	0.944	31.835	8.528	0.000

H1: the variable output volatility is normally distributed

H2: the variable output volatility is not normally distributed

From table 2, the p value is less than 0.05 indicating that the data set for output volatility is not normally distributed.

Table 4: Shapiro-Wilk W test for normal of financial development

Variable	Obs	W	V	z	Prob>z
Privatecre~y	889	0.932	38.635	9.006	0.000

H1: the variable Financial development is normally distributed

H2: the variable financial development is not normally distributed

From table 2, the p value is less than 0.05 indicating that the data set for financial development is not normally distributed.

Research Methodology

Empirical Methodology

Model 1

$$GDPgrowth = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 * CPI + \alpha_2 * TradeofGDP + \alpha_3 * Generalgovernmentfp + \alpha_4 * logGDPatmarketprice + \alpha_5 * Privatecreditbydep~y + \epsilon$$

Dependent variable

GDPgrowth – indicating economic growth

Independent variables

CPI- indicating inflation

TradeofGDP – indicating trade openness

Generalgovernmentfp- indicating government expenditure

logGDPatmarketprice – indicating economic size

Privatecreditbydep~y – indicating financial development

Model 2

$$\text{Outputvolatility} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \cdot \text{CPI} + \alpha_2 \cdot \text{TradeofGDP} + \alpha_3 \cdot \text{Generalgovernmentfp} + \alpha_4 \cdot \text{logGDPatmarketprice} + \alpha_5 \cdot \text{Privatecreditbydep~y} + \epsilon$$

Dependent variable

Outputvolatility – indicating annual volatility of output

Independent variables

CPI- indicating inflation

TradeofGDP – indicating trade openness

Generalgovernmentfp- indicating government expenditure

logGDPatmarketprice – indicating economic size

Privatecreditbydep~y – indicating financial development

Empirical results

Model 1

Table 5: regression Analysis (dependent variable Economic growth)

GDPgrowth	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
CPI	-.008	.003	-2.39	.017	-.014	-.001	**
logGDPatmarketprice~a	-.055	.063	-0.86	.389	-.179	.07	
Generalgovernmentfp~p	-.185	.026	-7.16	0	-.235	-.134	***
TradeofGDP	.005	.002	2.36	.018	.001	.009	**
Privatecreditbydep~y	-.017	.003	-5.40	0	-.024	-.011	***
Constant	9.01	1.775	5.07	0	5.525	12.494	***
Mean dependent var	3.651		SD dependent var	3.708			
R-squared	0.136		Number of obs	889			
F-test	27.774		Prob > F	0.000			
Akaike crit. (AIC)	4733.887		Bayesian crit. (BIC)	4762.627			

*** p<.01, ** p<.05, * p<.1

From table 5, the R squared value is 0.136 indicating that the independent variables can predict upto 13.6% of the variability in the dependent variable. The Prob > F is 0.000 indicating that in general the model is suitable in predicating the economic growth using the given independent variables. The coefficient for inflation (CPI) is -0.008 indicating that increase in inflation by one unit leads to decrease in Economic growth by 0.008. the coefficient for economic size (logGDPatmarketprice) is -0.055 indicating that increase in the economic size by one unit leads to decrease in the economic growth by 0.055. the coefficient for government expenditure (Generalgovernmentfp) is -0.185 indicating that increase in government expenditure by one unit leads to decrease in economic growth by 0.185. the coefficient for trade openness (TradeofGDP) is 0.005 indicating that increase in trade openness leads to increase in economic growth by 0.005. The coefficient for financial development (Privatecreditbydep~y) is -0.017 indicating that increase in financial development of country by one unit leads to decrease in economic growth by 0.017. The p value for inflation (CPI) is 0.017 which is less than 0.05 indicating that the variable inflation has a statistical significance in predicating the level of economic growth of a country. The p value for economic size (logGDPatmarketprice) is 0.389 which is more than 0.05

indicating that the variable economic size has no statistical significance in predicating the level of economic growth of a country. The p value for government expenditure (Generalgovernmentfp) is 0 which is less than 0.05 indicating that the variable government expenditure has statistical significance in predicating the level of economic growth of a country. The p value for trade openness (TradeofGDP) is 0.018 which is less than 0.05 indicating that the variable trade openness has statistical significance in predicating the level of economic growth of a country. The p value for financial development (Privatecreditbydep~y) is 0. which is less than 0.05 indicating that the variable financial development has statistical significance in predicating the level of economic growth of a country.

Hypothesis 1

From the regression model 1, it is clear that financial development is statistically significant in determining the level of economic growth hence the hypothesis 1 (there is significant statistical relationship between the financial development and the economic growth) is answered.

Model 2

Table 6: regression Analysis (dependent variable Volatility)

Outputvolatility	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
CPI	.003	.001	3.89	0	.002	.005	***
logGDPatmarketprice	.004	.003	1.36	.175	-.002	.01	
Generalgovernmentfp	.003	.001	2.32	.021	0	.005	**
TradeofGDP	0	0	0.65	.517	0	0	
Privatecreditbydep~y	-.001	0	-4.43	0	-.001	0	***
Constant	.147	.086	1.70	.09	-.023	.317	*

Mean dependent var	0.283	SD dependent var	0.170
R-squared	0.049	Number of obs	877
F-test	8.915	Prob > F	0.000
Akaike crit. (AIC)	-653.203	Bayesian crit. (BIC)	-624.544

*** p<.01, ** p<.05, * p<.1

From table 6, the R squared value is 0.049 indicating that the independent variables can predict upto 4.9% of the variability in the dependent variable. The Prob > F is 0.000 indicating that in general the model is suitable in predicating the Volatility using the given independent variables. The coefficient for inflation (CPI) is 0.003 indicating that increase in inflation by one unit leads to increase in volatility by 0.003. The coefficient for economic size (logGDPatmarketprice) is 0.004 indicating that increase in the economic size by one unit leads to increase in volatility by 0.004. the coefficient for government expenditure (Generalgovernmentfp) is 0.003 indicating that increase in government expenditure by one unit leads to increase in volatility by 0.003. the coefficient for trade openness (TradeofGDP) is 0.0 indicating that increase in trade openness by one unit leads to no change in volatility. The coefficient for financial development (Privatecreditbydep~y) is -0.001 indicating that increase in financial development of country by one unit leads to decrease in volatility by 0.001. The p value for inflation (CPI) is 0 which is less than 0.05 indicating that the variable inflation has a statistical significance in predicating the level of output volatility of a country. The p value for economic size (logGDPatmarketprice) is 0.175 which is more than 0.05 indicating that the variable economic size has no statistical significance in

predicating the level of output volatility of a country. The p value for government expenditure (Generalgovernmentfp) is 0.021 which is less than 0.05 indicating that the variable government expenditure has statistical significance in predicating the level of output volatility of a country. The p value for trade openness (TradeofGDP) is 0.517 which is less than 0.05 indicating that the variable trade openness has no statistical significance in predicating the level of output volatility of a country. The p value for financial development (Privatecreditbydep~y) is 0 which is less than 0.05 indicating that the variable financial development has statistical significance in predicating the level of output volatility of a country.

Hypothesis 2

From the regression model 2, it is clear that financial development is statistically significant in determining the level of output volatility hence the hypothesis 2 (there is significant statistical relationship between the financial development and the output volatility) is answered

Summary and conclusion

In summary there is significance relationship between economic growth and independent variables such as inflation, trade openness, government expenditure and financial development. There is also significant relationship between volatility and independent variables such as inflation, trade openness, government expenditure and financial development. In conclusion financial development impacts both the economic growth and volatility hence governments and policy makers should focus on financial development when dealing with economic growth and volatility of a certain country

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